

Saliency Maps as an Explainable AI Method in Medical Imaging: A Case Study on Brain Tumor Classification

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Abstract

Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) plays a crucial role in the field of medical imaging, where AI systems are used for clinical decision support and diagnostic processes. XAI aims to develop approaches that make machine learning (ML) models more transparent and interpretable, facilitating human-AI collaboration and improving trust. In medical imaging, early prediction of anomalies is vital, and understanding AI's decision-making process is crucial. Saliency maps are used to highlight important regions in an image and have been found a user-friendly explanation method for deep learning-based imaging tasks. They are widely used in many applications across various domains. There are different methods for generating saliency maps depending on the analysis and temporal occurrence. Ad-hoc methods are model-specific, while ante-hoc and post-hoc methods are independent of the model architecture. Post-hoc methods, such as activation-based, perturbation-based, and gradient-based methods, are commonly used for generating saliency maps. In this case study, we focus on the application of gradient-based saliency maps using Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) images to provide insights into brain tumor classification. To achieve this, we implemented a convolutional neural network (CNN) model on a benchmark brain MRI dataset and generated saliency maps. The results reveal that the tumor and its surrounding pixels play a significant role in the classification of brain MRIs, highlighting the importance of tumor shape in the classification process. Understanding these underlying mechanisms enhances the robustness, reliability, and accountability of AI systems used in brain tumor detection and classification.

Keywords: Explainable Artificial Intelligence, XAI, Saliency Map, Deep Learning, Clinical Decision Support, Brain Tumor Classification.

1. Introduction

1.1. Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) in Medical Imaging

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has inevitably become increasingly involved in clinical practice, in the form of clinical decision support systems (CDSS), assisting clinicians in the detection and diagnostic processes. It uses complex and high-performance machine learning (ML) models trained on large sets of medical data. Since state-of-the-art ML systems are getting more sophisticated, they are also becoming less interpretable, hence black-box solutions. Explainability of the AI model is essential in the medical domain, where understanding the reason for a decision is as important as the decision itself (Amann, Blasimme, Vayena, Frey, & Madai, 2020; Sina, Zarei, & Ragan, 2021). At the point of comprehensibility of AI/ML systems, the paradigm of eXplainable AI (XAI) comes into the scene. To understand, and eventually improve the inner dynamics of a model, XAI aims at developing approaches for making ML models more transparent and interpretable, so users can understand how the model is making decisions. Moreover, explainability provides the ability to overlook the model's possible bottlenecks and identify potential biases, yielding to make necessary curations and calibrations on it, increasing trust, and facilitating human-AI communication and collaboration (Rasheed, et al., 2022). In the field of medical imaging, the purpose of AI is to support clinicians to make an informed decision in the diagnostic procedures as early as possible since it is vital to predict initial stages in case of a malignancy. Proper classification of clinical findings needs to be

evidence-based and trustworthy. Medical experts in studies tend to review explanations provided by AI when its predictions align with their hypotheses or help resolve disagreements, especially in medical imaging tasks (Jin, Li, & Hamarneh, 2021). Saliency maps are one of the preferred user-friendly explanation methods.

1.2. Saliency Maps in Computer Vision and Medical Imaging

In computer vision (CV), saliency maps are seen as a visualization technique to highlight the most key features of an input that contribute to the output of an AI model (Lamichhane, Carli, & Battisti, 2023). Therefore, they provide a way to understand which parts of the input data are influencing the model's decision-making process. This makes them widely used in Deep Learning (DL)-based image processing tasks, such as object detection, image segmentation, and visual attention modelling (Nauta, et al., 2022). Saliency maps have proven to be valuable in various applications and domains, not only in computer vision, but also in natural language processing and generation, recommendation systems, fraud, and anomaly detection, and human-computer interaction (Rahimi & Jain, 2022; RichardWebster, Hu, Fieldhouse, & Kitware, 2022; Andrushia, Sagayam, Dang, Pomplun, & Quach, 2021), etc. Several methods have been proposed to generate saliency maps in XAI. It is important to design methods that are specifically suited for the medical field due to its unique characteristics (Reyes, et al., 2020). Additionally, these methods vary depending on factors such as the type of input data (e.g., acquisition modality, additional clinical data) and the architecture of the AI model (Singh, Sengupta, & Lakshminarayanan, 2020). Saliency maps are also classified in terms of temporal occurrence. Ad-hoc, ante-hoc, and post-hoc saliency maps are three distinct approaches for analysing and interpreting saliency in various domains. Each approach serves different purposes in saliency analysis and interpretation. Ante-hoc saliency maps, also known as pre-hoc saliency maps, are created in advance before any specific task or analysis aiming to capture and represent the inherent salient features or regions in the input data, irrespective of any specific task or application. Post-hoc saliency maps are generated after the completion of a specific task or analysis. Post-hoc saliency maps help in understanding the underlying factors that influenced the results and provide insights into the decision-making process or the causes of certain outcomes (Ali, et al., 2023). Three most common approaches to generate *Post-Hoc saliency maps*; *activation-based methods* that work by aggregating neuron activation signals in a deep neural network and visualizing signals in the input space, *perturbation-based methods* that operate by manipulating input features and observing their respective output to measure their difference from the original output, and finally *gradient-based methods*, that function by calculating the partial derivative of a prediction for an input feature. *Gradient-based methods* compute the importance of input features by examining the gradients of the output class for the input data. These methods leverage the gradient information to identify which input features contribute most significantly to the final prediction (Vries, et al., 2023).

2. A Case-Study

Some research studies in the field of medical image classification have undertaken analyses to find out the significance of individual input image pixels in influencing the final prediction using different saliency methods. In their study, Ayhan et al. (Ayhan, et al., 2022) validated perturbation-based saliency maps compared with expert annotations for the detection of diabetic retinopathy and neovascular age-related macular degeneration using retinal fundus images and optical coherence tomography scans. In another study (Wang, 2021), Wang examined gradient-based saliency maps of an AI model and provided valuable insights into the regions of input X-ray images that hold significance in the model's estimation of hand bone age. Amorim et al (Amorim, Abreu, Santos, Cortes, & Vila, 2023) assessed the fidelity of the saliency maps by introducing inherent perturbations in histopathological images of breast cancer, subsequently discovering that saliency maps based on gradients exhibit a correlation with the presence of tumor evidence within the image. Brain tumor detection is one of the hottest topics in medical image research (Muhammad, Khan, Ser, & Albuquerque, 2021; Ranjbarzadeh, Caputo, Tirkolaee, Ghouschi, & Bendeche, 2022). Understanding how AI models classify brain MRI images is crucial for reliable and accountable brain tumor detection. In their study, Wojciech et al. (Chmiel, Kwiecie, & Motyka,

2023) demonstrate that integrating saliency regions with various CNNs is effective for brain tumor detection in X-ray images. However, MRI imaging is extensively employed in the diagnosis of brain tumors and various medical conditions, surpassing X-ray imaging in terms of superior soft tissue visualization and non-invasiveness. This research study focuses on the interpretability of the CNN model in tumor classification by generating post-hoc, gradient-based saliency maps on brain MRI images as a novelty. The BR35H::Brain Tumor Detection 2020 dataset (Hamada, 2020) of brain MRIs dataset is used in the case study. In brain MRIs, it is seen that the tumor and its surrounding pixels are of high importance in the classification of images with tumors. These results highlight that the tumor and its shape in brain MRIs play a significant role in classification.

2.1. Dataset

BR35H dataset (Hamada, 2020) contains 1500 negative and 1500 positive MRIs of brain tumors. The dataset is publicly accessible at <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/ahmedhamada0/brain-tumor-detection>. Each MRI image is two-dimensional (2D) and has different dimension sizes. Twenty percent of the images from this dataset are used for testing the model. Before feeding to the DL model, the original images are pre-processed. They rescaled to a size 128x128, and the data type converted to float32. Figure 1 shows some examples from the used dataset. The title of each image indicates the image's label (yes/no).

Figure 1 Examples of MR images from BR35H Dataset.

2.2. The Deep Learning Model

A comparatively straightforward CNN architecture was implemented. The Keras package is used to build the proposed models, with TensorFlow (Abadi, et al., 2016) as the backend. The proposed model consists of two convolutional layers followed by two dense layers preceding the softmax layers and 2x2 max-pooling was applied to each convolutional layer's output of models. The 2D model's input data shape is 128x128. The activation function of the convolution output of the model was ReLU. In the training and validation processes, implemented models were trained for fifty epochs. The architecture of the model is demonstrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The Architecture of implemented CNN Model

2.3. Saliency Maps of the models:

Mathematically, a saliency map is the derivative of the class probability of the input image. The calculated saliency maps were created with the TensorFlow library which provides a built-in function. The study involved the calculation of saliency maps for MRI images containing tumors, specifically examining two groups: correctly predicted MRIs (comprising eight images) and misclassified MRIs (consisting of two images). As the primary focus of this investigation was to evaluate the influence of tumor presence on classification, saliency maps for healthy brain images (those without tumors) were not generated. By directing attention solely to tumor-related images, the study aimed to gain valuable insights into the impact of tumor presence on the classification process.

The third figure (Figure 3) of this study presents a comparative analysis comprising two brain MRI images containing tumors that were misclassified by the DL model, along with their respective saliency maps. Within this figure, the tumor regions are visually emphasized through square markings overlaid on the MRI images. Notably, an observation is made that the saliency maps for these images fail to effectively highlight the tumor regions. Consequently, it becomes evident that these tumors occupy a more extensive spatial extent within the brain compared to the accurately predicted tumors (Figure 4), leading to blurred boundaries and a lack of distinctiveness in the corresponding saliency maps.

Figure 4 in the study displays the MRI collection, including brain tumor cases accurately predicted by the model. In contrast to Figure 3, Figure 4 visually highlights regions associated with the presence of tumors on the saliency maps using squares, rather than on MRI images. In this way, distinctive pixels are shown to be concentrated around the tumor, presenting accurately classified MRI images and their corresponding saliency maps. This demonstration provides valuable information that contributes significantly to the prediction of the model.

Figure 3 shows FALSE predicted 2 MRIs with brain tumors and related saliency maps of them. Tumors in MRI images were visually depicted using squares to show regions.

Brain MRIs with Tumor and predicted as TRUE

Figure 4 shows TRUE predicted 8 MRIs with brain tumors and related saliency maps of them. To illustrate the specific regions which coincided with the tumor coordinates in the MRI images, salient regions on the maps were visually depicted using squares.

3. Results

The Confusion Matrix (CM) is a fundamental tool for assessing the performance of a binary or categorical classifier. The F1 score (or Dice similarity coefficient) metric was commonly used to measure the ratio of overlap for both classes by taking harmonic mean precision formulated as $TP/(TP + FP)$ and recall(sensitivity) formulated as $TP/(TP + FN)$, derived from the confusion matrix. The CNN model's CM and calculated metrics from CM are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Confusion Matrix for 2-Class Classification

Confusion Matrix				Calculated Metrics			
Predicted				Precision	Recall	F1-score	Sample Number
	No	Yes					
Actual	No	29	6	0.85	0.83	0.84	35
	Yes	5	16	0.73	0.76	0.74	21

4. Discussions

The primary objective of this study was not to develop a highly accurate model. Rather, our focus was on interpreting the model's estimation using saliency maps. However, the accuracy metrics of the implemented model are presented in the results section to provide a quantitative measure of its predictive capabilities. Consequently, we will beware of discussing a model with improved accuracy in this context.

The saliency maps generated using gradient-based analysis revealed that the DL model's predictions strongly focus on areas corresponding to tumor presence in the given MRI image. This finding provides valuable insights into how the model makes decisions. However, they often lack a clear threshold to determine the significance of salient regions and may struggle to capture context and global relationships in complex scenes or images. During the subsequent discussion, we interpreted the saliency maps alongside available information and expert input from the field. We took these limitations into account, aiming to provide reliable and meaningful results.

Upon careful examination of the saliency maps depicted in the provided figures, it becomes apparent that the regions corresponding to the bones in the skull-stripping influence the decision-making process of the DL model. Consequently, incorporating a preprocessing step that involves bone extraction before training the model can improve accuracy. This bone extraction process would effectively shift the attention of the model towards the soft tissue regions, thereby enhancing its capacity to classify brain tumors more accurately.

The misclassified tumor images become evident that these tumors possess more complicated shapes. These unsteady shapes are challenging for the model to accurately detect. Consequently, to increase accuracy in tumor classification, it is necessary to enrich the dataset with a broader range of brain MRI images that include tumors exhibiting complex shapes. By training the model with an expanded dataset comprising such diverse tumor shapes, it is expected to strengthen its ability to discern and classify tumors with higher precision and reliability.

There are advantages and drawbacks to using saliency maps in medical image processing. Interpretability is the most significant of its benefits since the aim is to draw a visual explanation for the model's decision-making process, and eventually, to explain the inner workings and improve in case of necessity. They can also guide attention by indicating the most informative regions in an image, drawing a region of interest (ROI), and enabling more efficient processing on this focus. For the detection tasks, attention guidance can enhance performance by reducing the search space and improving accuracy.

5. Conclusions

The field of XAI is still evolving, and there is ongoing research and development aimed at improving the interpretability and explainability of AI models. Although they are not the sole solution, saliency maps remain a valuable tool in this domain, and new methods will continue to emerge as the field progresses. In our conducted case study, we have arrived at the finding that incorporating a preprocessing step that involves bone extraction before model training will be beneficial, as it will redirect the model's attention towards soft tissue regions, leading to improved accuracy in classifying brain tumors using MRI images. Furthermore, the misclassification reveals that the model struggles with tumors exhibiting complex shapes. To enhance classification accuracy, it is essential to enrich the dataset with a broader range of brain MRI images that encompass tumors with diverse and intricate shapes. Finally, the incorporation and careful interpretation of saliency maps can provide valuable insights, improve model performance, and facilitate the understanding of AI model behaviour in medical image processing.

However, it is essential to consider both the benefits and drawbacks of using saliency maps to ensure their appropriate and effective utilization in practical applications.

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